

Effect of buffers and ionic strength on the stability constant of complexes of iron(III) with salicylic acid and its derivatives

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Abstract : The 1 : 1 complex formed by iron(II) with salicylic acid and its seven derivatives were studied by spectrophotometry and the effect of phthalate-HCl and KCl-HCl buffers on the value of stability constants of 1 : 1 complex determined by spectrophotometry, was evaluated. The thermodynamic value of stability constant of each system was determined by obtaining the values at different ionic strength and extrapolating them to zero ionic strength. For extrapolation, a new approach was made which gives a straight line curve making it easier to extrapolate at zero ionic strength to get the thermodynamic value thus reducing the uncertainty in extrapolation.

Keywords : Stability constants, salicylic acid, iron(III) complexes.

Iron(III) forms colored complex with salicylic acid and its derivatives. A number of workers have studied these systems and determined the stability constant of 1 : 1 and higher complexes¹. Salicylic acid releases proton when it undergoes complex formation with iron(III) and therefore it is necessary to fix the pH. Usually one uses a buffer solution for fixing the pH for making measurements. It has already reported in the literature² that citrate, acetate, chloroacetate and phosphate buffers compete with salicylic acid. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to see the effect of buffers like phthalate-HCl and Clark and Lubes KCl-HCl buffer in the determination of stability constant of the complex formed by Fe^{III} with salicylic acid and seven of its derivatives. Further in order to determine the thermodynamic value of stability constant the conditional stability constant at different ionic strength was obtained and then extrapolated to zero ionic strength. A new methodology has been adopted in this work to find out the thermodynamic value using a linear plot.

Results and discussion

In the lower range of pH (1–3), Fe^{III} forms 1 : 1 complex with salicylic acid and its derivatives. The λ_{max} of these complexes depends on various substituent present in salicylic acid ring and the range of λ_{max} varied from 500–560 nm which falls in the visible region of the spectrum and therefore the complex can be studied by spectrophotometry.

Fe^{III} ion and ligands were mixed in 1 : 1 ratio and four solutions having different total concentrations ($4.0\text{--}6.4 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³) were prepared for each system. In each solution 2 ml of HClO₄ (0.1 mol dm⁻³), 5 ml of NaClO₄ (1 M) and 5 ml of phthalate buffer solutions were added. The total volume was made upto 50 ml. The pH of these solutions was measured after recording absorbance at λ_{max} and was found to be 2.35 ± 0.05 . In order to determine the stability constant k_1' which is given by $k_1' = [\text{FeL}]/[\text{Fe}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]$, the molar absorptivity was determined for each system using the method described elsewhere³. From molar absorptivity, k_1' value was determined for each system at different metal-ligand concentrations. For some systems k_1' were also determined at pH 2.35, adjusted with dil. HClO₄ solution. Both the results are summarized in Table 1. When k_1' values determined with buffer, it was observed that considerable lowering in the value of k_1' takes place due to the presence of the buffer which shows that the phthalate buffer competes with ligand. Similar results were also recorded with Clark and Lubes KCl-HCl buffer. Here the enhanced Cl⁻ ion concentration is perhaps responsible for lowering of stability constant value as at high concentration, the Cl⁻ ion also competes with the ligand.

If we consider the dissociation of both carboxyl and phenolic group and represent the dissociation constants as

Note

K_{carboxyl} and K_{phenolic} respectively then the stability constant k_1 which is $[\text{FeL}]/[\text{Fe}][\text{L}]$ takes the form $k_1 = k_1' \cdot \Phi$, where $\Phi = 1 + [\text{H}^+]/K_{\text{phenolic}} + [\text{H}^+]^2/(K_{\text{carboxyl}}K_{\text{phenolic}})$, where $[\text{H}^+]$ represents hydrogen ion concentration.

To study the effect of ionic strength on k_1 and k_1' , metal ion and ligand were mixed in 1 : 1 ratio. For each system 6-7 solutions were prepared and the ionic strength was varied in the range 0.5–0.005 using the required amount of sodium perchlorate. The pH of all the solutions was adjusted to 2.35 ± 0.05 with the help of dilute perchloric acid and the absorbance was measured at λ_{max} . The k_1' values were calculated using the molar absorptivity (ϵ_c) value obtained as above. For extrapolation the value of k_1' at different ionic strengths usually $\log k_1'$ is plotted against \sqrt{I}^4 which results in a hyperbolic curve. Here I is ionic strength of the solution. The extrapolation of such curve to zero ionic strength involves greater uncertainty in the extrapolated value. Therefore a new approach had been adopted in which $\log k_1'$ is plotted against $[\sqrt{I}/(1 + \sqrt{I}) - 0.2I]$. While determining the pK value of salicylic acid and its derivatives it has been observed⁵ that instead of plotting pK against \sqrt{I} , if the pK is plotted against $[\sqrt{I}/(1 + \sqrt{I}) - 0.2I]$ then one get a straight line which makes the extrapolation of pK value to zero ionic strength with minimum uncertainty. In present case $\log k_1'$ values determined at different ionic strength were plotted against $[\sqrt{I}/(1 + \sqrt{I}) - 0.2I]$. This resulted in a straight line and from extrapolation of value at zero ionic strength the thermodynamic value ($\log {}^T k_1'$) was also determined.

In order to determine the $\log k_1$ value at different ionic strength it became necessary to find out the K_{carboxyl} and K_{phenolic} values at these ionic strengths. Using the methods described elsewhere the dissociation constants were evaluated at different ionic strengths, subsequently the value of $\log k_1$ was calculated from k_1' , K_{carboxyl} and K_{phenolic} at each value of ionic strength. The value of $\log k_1$ was plotted against $[\sqrt{I}/(1 + \sqrt{I}) - 0.2I]$ which resulted in a straight line and from extrapolation to zero ionic strength the thermodynamic value ($\log {}^T k_1$) was obtained. Results of this system are summarized in Table 2.

Experimental

Reagent grade samples of the following salicylic acids were employed : (i) 2-hydroxybenzoic acid (SA), (B.D.H.), (ii) 2-hydroxy, 3-methylbenzoic acid (3-MSA), (B.D.H.), (iii) 2-hydroxy, 4-methylbenzoic acid (4-MSA), (K and K Lab), (iv) 2-hydroxy, 5-methylbenzoic acid (5-MSA), (K and K Lab), (v) 2-hydroxy, 5-sulphobenzoic acid (5-SSA), (E. Merck), (vi) 2-hydroxy, 3-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid

(3-M, 5-SSA), (vii) 2-hydroxy, 4-methyl, 5-sulphobenzoic acid (4-M, 5-SSA), (viii) 2-hydroxy, 3-sulpho, 5-methylbenzoic acid (3-S, 5-MSA). Where M stands for $-\text{CH}_3$ group and S for $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. These acids (vi) to (viii) were prepared as described earlier⁶.

Table 1. Effect of phthalate buffer

pH = 2.35 ± 0.05 , $I = 0.1$

Ligand	$M^0 \times 10^4$	$L^0 \times 10^4$	A (with buffer)	$k_1' \times 10^4$	A (without buffer)	$k_1' \times 10^4$
SA	2.0	2.0	0.200	2.86	0.2375	4.42
	2.4	2.4	0.250	1.97	0.2875	3.88
	2.8	2.8	0.300	1.49	0.3500	4.41
	3.2	3.2	0.290	1.85	—	—
3-MSA	2.0	2.0	0.150	0.752	0.2250	2.01
	2.4	2.4	0.194	0.771	—	—
	2.8	2.8	0.238	0.768	0.3125	2.24
	3.2	3.2	0.281	0.741	0.3625	2.11
4-MSA	2.0	2.0	0.194	1.68	0.2324	4.04
	2.4	2.4	0.244	1.69	0.2875	3.84
	2.8	2.8	0.294	1.66	0.3438	3.85
	3.2	3.2	0.344	1.62	0.4062	4.26
5-MSA	2.0	2.0	0.218	1.74	0.2625	4.18
	2.4	2.4	0.275	1.77	0.3250	4.22
	2.8	2.8	0.337	1.89	0.3875	4.18
	3.2	3.2	0.400	2.00	0.4500	4.10
5-SSA	2.0	2.0	0.294	6.68	—	—
	2.4	2.4	0.356	5.96	0.3281	9.26
	2.8	2.8	0.419	5.46	0.3750	10.60
	3.4	3.4	0.519	5.30	—	—
3-M,	2.0	2.0	0.275	3.40	0.2938	5.00
5-SSA	2.4	2.4	0.338	3.23	0.3625	5.02
	2.8	2.8	0.400	3.01	0.4312	4.95
	3.2	3.2	0.468	3.04	0.5000	4.84
4-M,	2.0	2.0	0.294	3.20	0.3250	5.51
5-SSA	2.4	2.4	0.362	3.06	0.4000	5.80
	2.8	2.8	0.431	2.94	0.4312	5.71
	3.2	3.2	0.506	3.04	0.5500	5.57
3-S,	2.0	2.0	0.312	4.05	0.3375	6.76
5-MSA	2.4	2.4	0.381	3.74	0.4188	7.35
	2.8	2.8	0.456	3.77	—	—
	3.2	3.2	0.532	3.79	0.5688	6.48

M^0 and L^0 are respectively the total metal ion and total ligand concentrations in mol dm^{-3} .

Table 2. Values of k_1 and k_1' at different ionic strengths

pH = 2.35 ± 0.05, $M^0 = L^0 = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³

System	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_c	Thermodynamic value $\log^T k_1'$	Thermodynamic value $\log^T k_1$
Fe ^{III} -SA	530	1660	5.21	17.29
Fe ^{III} -3-MSA	556	1660	4.86	17.91
Fe ^{III} -4-MSA	534	1663	5.03	17.52
Fe ^{III} -5-MSA	560	1852	5.06	17.72
Fe ^{III} -5-SSA	506	1931	5.44	16.47
Fe ^{III} -3-M, 5-SSA	530	2013	5.29	16.93
Fe ^{III} -4-M, 5-SSA	510	2177	5.17	16.72
Fe ^{III} -3-S, 5-MSA	546	2213	5.22	17.75

A stock solution of ferric chloride in dilute HClO₄ was prepared and standardized titrimetrically against standard dichromate solution. CO₂ free NaOH and HClO₄ solutions were used for bringing the pH at the desired value. Solutions of acids and alkalis were standardized by conventional titrimetric methods. NaClO₄ was used as a background electrolyte. For fixing the lower pH value of metal complexes (pH = 2.35) Clark and Lubes buffer mixture was prepared by mixing 39.60 ml of 0.1 N HCl with 50 ml of 0.1 N potassium hydrogen phthalate solution and raising the volume to 100 ml with water.

All pH measurements were made with a universal pH meter (Redelkis OP-204, Hungary) with glass and calomel electrodes. The pH meter has a least count of 0.05 pH unit. The absorption spectra was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 UV-Vis or SF-4 USSR spectrophotometer. Measurements were done at room temperature at 25 ± 1°. The pH meter readings were converted into [H⁺] using the method of McBryde⁷.

The reaction between Fe^{III} and salicylic acids can be shown to take place as

The charges are omitted for simplicity. The equilibrium constant for reaction (1) can be expressed as

$$k_1'' = \frac{[\text{FeL}][\text{H}]^2}{[\text{Fe}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]} \quad (2)$$

If the reaction is performed under constant pH, [H] becomes constant which could be taken up with k_1'' to give a new constant k_1' , which is given by

$$k_1' = \frac{[\text{FeL}]}{[\text{Fe}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]} = \frac{k_1''}{[\text{H}]^2} \quad (3)$$

k_1' is conditional stability constant. If the pH is varied the value would also vary.

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